

The Influence of Visual Sensory Marketing on Brand E-Reputation and Purchase Intention in the digital age: A Quantitative Bibliometric Review (2015–2025)

L'influence du marketing sensoriel visuel sur l'e-réputation des marques et l'intention d'achat à l'ère du numérique : Une analyse bibliométrique quantitative (2015–2025)

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Abstract

In a context where digital environments are redefining interactions between brands and consumers, visual sensory marketing is asserting itself as a strategic lever for differentiation. This study proposes a quantitative bibliometric review of scientific publications published between 2015 and 2025, focusing on the relationship between visual sensory marketing, e-reputation and purchase intention. Based on a corpus of 1570 articles from the Web Of Science database, the analysis highlights the influence of visual stimuli (color, typography, design) on brand perception and digital credibility. The results, obtained using VOSviewer and Excel tools, reveal the existence of thematic clusters where e-reputation plays a mediating role between visual sensory experience and the purchase decision. Co-occurrence mapping shows that consumer trust, emotion and commitment are key variables in this process of influence. This research makes an original contribution by crossing three dimensions rarely analyzed jointly: sensory visual marketing, online reputation and purchase intention. It offers a new approach to digital marketing, where visual impact and digital reputation shape the perceived value of brands.

Keywords: Visual sensory marketing; E-reputation; Purchase intention; bibliometric review.

Résumé

Dans un contexte où les environnements numériques redéfinissent les interactions entre marques et consommateurs, le marketing sensoriel visuel s'affirme comme un levier stratégique de différenciation. Cette étude propose une revue bibliométrique quantitative des publications scientifiques parues entre 2015 et 2025, centrée sur la relation entre marketing sensoriel visuel, e-réputation et intention d'achat. Basée sur un corpus de 1 570 articles issus de la base de données Web Of Science, l'analyse met en évidence l'influence des stimuli visuels (couleur, typographie, design) sur la perception de la marque et sa crédibilité numérique. Les résultats, obtenus grâce aux outils VOSviewer et Excel, révèlent l'existence de clusters thématiques où l'e-réputation joue un rôle médiateur entre l'expérience sensorielle visuelle et la décision d'achat. La cartographie des cooccurrences montre que la confiance, l'émotion et l'engagement des consommateurs sont des variables clés de ce processus d'influence. Cette recherche apporte une contribution originale en croisant trois dimensions rarement analysées conjointement : le marketing sensoriel visuel, la réputation en ligne et l'intention d'achat. Elle propose une nouvelle approche du marketing numérique, où l'influence visuel et la réputation numérique façonnent la valeur perçue des marques.

Mots clés : Marketing sensoriel visuel ; E-réputation ; Intention d'achat ; Revue bibliométrique.

Introduction

In the digital age, brands evolve in an environment where online visibility and consumer perception directly condition their commercial performance. The rise of digital platforms and social networks has profoundly transformed the customer-brand relationship, giving e-reputation a central role in building trust and in purchasing decisions (Berthon et al., 2012; Hajli, 2014). In this context, visual sensorial marketing, which mobilizes elements such as color, design, typography and layout, is emerging as a major strategic lever. It not only acts as an initial point of contact between the brand and its audience, but also influences memorization, evaluation and the propensity to recommend or purchase a product (Pelet & Papadopoulou, 2012).

Although sensorial marketing has been widely explored in academic literature, particularly from the customer experience angle (Schmitt, 1999), few studies have sought to analyze the specific interrelationships between visual marketing, e-reputation and purchase intention in a digital context. Yet these three dimensions appear closely linked : Visual exposure shapes first impressions, stimulates affective and cognitive reactions, and guides online social behaviors, which in turn contribute to a brand's digital reputation (Cyr et al., 2010; Labrecque & Milne, 2012). This reputation, in turn, constitutes social proof strongly influencing purchase intention (Chevalier & Mayzlin, 2006; Hajli, 2014).

In response to this gap, the present study proposes to carry out a quantitative bibliometric review of the scientific literature on these three concepts. The aim is twofold : on the one hand, to map the dominant research axes, semantic connections and evolutionary dynamics of the field; on the other, to propose an integrated reading of the role of visual sensory marketing in the consumer decision-making process via e-reputation (Donthu et al., 2021).

The central question guiding this research is: **What is the influence of visual sensory marketing on consumer purchase intention, through the prism of e-reputation?**

To answer this question, this paper is organized as follows: it begins with a theoretical framework explaining the three key concepts, followed by a methodological presentation of the bibliometric analysis carried out. The results are then presented and interpreted, before giving way to a critical discussion, a general summary and prospects for future research.

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2012; Hajli, 2014). Within this context, visual sensory marketing—which mobilizes elements such as color, design, typography, and layout—emerges as a key strategic lever. It not only serves as the initial point of contact between the brand and its audience, but also influences memorization, evaluation, and the propensity to recommend or purchase a product (Pelet & Papadopoulou, 2012).

Although sensory marketing has been extensively explored in the academic literature, particularly from the customer experience perspective (Schmitt, 1999), few studies have specifically examined the mediating role of e-reputation in the relationship between visual sensory marketing and purchase intention in digital environments. Yet, these three dimensions appear intrinsically linked: visual exposure shapes first impressions, stimulates affective and cognitive reactions, and drives online social behaviors, which, in turn, contribute to a brand's digital reputation (Cyr et al., 2010; Labrecque & Milne, 2012). This reputation subsequently serves as social proof that strongly influences purchase intention (Chevalier & Mayzlin, 2006; Hajli, 2014).

To address this gap, the present study conducts a quantitative bibliometric analysis of the scientific literature on these three interrelated concepts, based solely on publications indexed in the Web of Science database. The methodology follows the PRISMA protocol to ensure transparency in the article selection process and employs VOSviewer software, along with Microsoft Excel, to analyze keyword co-occurrences, temporal trends, and thematic clusters. The objective is twofold: (1) to map dominant research themes, semantic connections, and the field's evolutionary dynamics; and (2) to provide an integrated understanding of how visual sensory marketing influences consumer decision-making through the mediating effect of e-reputation (Donthu et al., 2021).

The central research question guiding this investigation is: **What is the influence of visual sensory marketing on consumer purchase intention, through the mediating role of e-reputation?**

This paper is structured as follows: first, the theoretical framework outlines the three key concepts; second, the methodology presents the bibliometric approach adopted; third, the results are analyzed and interpreted; and finally, the discussion section offers a critical reflection, managerial implications, and suggestions for future research.

1. Theoretical framework

1.1. Visual sensorial marketing: An essential dimension for capturing attention and influencing perception

Sensorial marketing is an approach that aims to appeal to the consumer's five senses in order to enrich their experience and influence their purchasing behavior. Among its various components (visual, auditory, olfactory, gustatory and tactile), the visual dimension is particularly central in digital environments where sensory interactions are limited primarily to sight (Krishna, 2012).

Elements such as color, images, typography and even the layout of content play a decisive role in how a brand is perceived. For example, certain colors are associated with specific emotions: blue evokes confidence and security, red energy and urgency, while green is linked to nature and serenity (Labrecque & Milne, 2012). These visual choices not only help to attract consumers' attention, but also convey values and reinforce the brand's personality (Aslam, 2006).

The perceived quality of visual design also impacts brand credibility in the digital environment. An aesthetically pleasing website is often perceived as more professional and reliable, which positively influences visitor attitudes (Cyr et al., 2010).

In the context of our research, this means that visual sensory marketing acts as the first point of contact that shapes the initial perception of the brand, thus paving the way for e-reputation. However, despite its acknowledged impact, visual sensory marketing in the digital realm remains subject to contextual and cultural contingencies. The same visual cues may generate divergent perceptions across markets, and the abundance of visual stimuli in online environments can lead to consumer fatigue or reduced attention (Bouaddi et al., 2024). This suggests that, while impactful, the effectiveness of visual sensory strategies must be critically assessed in relation to audience characteristics and evolving digital trends.

1.2. E-reputation: A strategic intangible asset in the digital environment

E-reputation refers to the collective perception of a brand by Internet users, based on information available online. It is built from content disseminated by the brand itself, but also ; and above all; from social interactions such as consumer reviews, comments on social networks, and recommendations on specialized platforms (Berthon et al., 2012).

In a context where consumers massively refer to online reviews before making a purchasing decision, a company's digital reputation has become a crucial differentiating factor(Ouariti et

al., 2020). A positive e-reputation improves perceived brand credibility, boosts consumer confidence, and increases purchase intent (Hajli, 2014). Conversely, negative signals or poorly managed reviews can quickly deteriorate a brand's image and deter potential buyers.

This link between visual marketing and e-reputation is direct: a consistent, engaging visual identity encourages positive sharing on social networks, strengthens community engagement and stimulates favorable online interactions. In other words, visual design acts as a catalyst for digital reputation. (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010) Yet, e-reputation is inherently volatile, being shaped not only by deliberate brand strategies but also by uncontrolled user-generated content. The amplification effects of social media can exacerbate reputational risks (Nambang-Kagnolema, 2025), making visual coherence insufficient on its own to ensure a positive digital image. This highlights the need for brands to combine aesthetic strategies with proactive reputation management, suggesting that visual marketing's influence on e-reputation is neither automatic nor universally positive.

1.3. Purchase intention: The culmination of perceptions and brand reputation

Purchase intention corresponds to a consumer's expressed or implicit desire to acquire a given product or service. It is influenced by several factors, including perceived product quality, brand trust and overall user experience (Pavlou & Fygenon, 2006).

Visual marketing helps shape this intention by creating an engaging sensory experience that facilitates brand recall and arouses positive emotions. At the same time, a solid e-reputation acts as reassuring social proof, removing any final hesitations before the act of purchase (Chevalier & Mayzlin, 2006). In short, it's the combination of the sensory influence of visual marketing and the confidence generated by e-reputation that encourages consumers to take the plunge.

In our research, purchase intention is therefore the end result of a process of cross-influence, in another way, the quality of visual communication feeds e-reputation, which in turn reinforces the propensity to buy. (Marwan et al., 2024) Nevertheless, purchase intention is not solely determined by visual appeal or reputational signals; it is also influenced by situational factors such as price sensitivity, product availability, and competing offers. Moreover, consumers may exhibit an intention-behavior gap, where expressed willingness to purchase does not translate into actual buying behavior (Boukabiya & Benaceur, 2020). This calls for a nuanced interpretation of visual and reputational influences, acknowledging that they operate within a broader, more complex decision-making ecosystem.

2. Methodology

In order to rigorously answer our research question, we opted for a quantitative bibliometric review, an approach recognized for its ability to synthesize and map accumulated knowledge in a specific field (Donthu et al., 2021). This method provides an objective overview of academic contributions and identifies priority research areas, key conceptual relationships and gaps in the literature.

Our approach was structured around three main stages: rigorous selection of studies, bibliometric analysis using specialized tools, and detailed interpretation of the results obtained.

2.1. Selection of relevant studies

2.1.1 Choice of database

In this study, the Web of Science (WoS) database was selected as the primary source for data extraction due to its rigorous indexing criteria, multidisciplinary scope, and high-quality peer-reviewed content. WoS is widely recognized as one of the most comprehensive and reliable platforms for bibliometric research, offering advanced tools for citation tracking, keyword analysis, and scholarly mapping. Its inclusion of leading journals across the fields of marketing, management, psychology, and information sciences ensures the relevance and academic rigor of the articles retrieved for this analysis. (Mongeon & Paul-Hus, 2016).

2.1.2 Period of analysis

We have restricted our analysis to publications published between 2015 and 2025, a period during which digital visual marketing practices and the influence of social networks on e-reputation have developed strongly (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010; Krishna, 2012). This period guarantees the relevance and timeliness of the selected research.

2.1.3 Documentary search strategy

The search strategy was based on combinations of keywords rigorously chosen to reflect the central concepts of our problematic:

- Visual sensory marketing
- E-reputation
- Purchase intention.

These keywords were searched in the titles, abstracts and keywords of the articles to maximize the relevance of the corpus.

2.1.4 Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion: We have selected empirical and theoretical studies focusing specifically on the impact of sensory visual marketing on brand perception, e-reputation and purchase intention. Also included was research exploring the relationships between these concepts in the context of digital environments and social platforms.

Exclusion: Non-peer-reviewed studies, articles not available in full text, and publications focusing on other sensory dimensions (auditory, olfactory, gustatory, tactile) were excluded. (Tranfield et al., 2003).

2.1.5 PRISMA selection protocol

The selection process followed the **PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses)** guidelines to ensure methodological transparency and reproducibility (Ed-Dafali et al., 2025). The process unfolded as follows:

- **Identification** – Retrieval of all potentially relevant publications from WoS using the predefined search terms.
- **Screening** – Removal of duplicates, followed by title screening to exclude clearly irrelevant studies.
- **Eligibility** – Abstract review to assess alignment with inclusion criteria; in ambiguous cases, the introduction or theoretical framework was consulted.
- **Inclusion** – Final selection of articles meeting all inclusion criteria.

A **double-check validation** was conducted by two independent researchers to reduce selection bias (Kitchenham, 2004).

From a total of 3,655 initial publications, a final sample of 1,082 articles was selected.

Tableau N°1 : Evolution of the selection process

Selection stage	Number of articles
Records identified	3 799
Records screened after removing duplicates	3,655
Records excluded after title/abstract screening	1 562
Full-text articles assessed for eligibility	2,093
Final articles included in the bibliometric analysis	1570

Source: Authors

2.2. Bibliometric analysis

To analyze and visualize the selected corpus, we have mobilized several complementary tools to provide both a quantitative and visual analysis.

VOSviewer

VOSviewer was used for bibliometric mapping of co-occurrence networks, identification of thematic clusters, and visualization of relationships between the key concepts in our study (van Eck & Waltman, 2010). We performed:

- Key term co-occurrence analysis to detect dominant themes in each concept.
- Co-occurrence analysis to reveal connections between concepts and thematic clustering to group converging searches.

Excel

Excel was also used for descriptive analysis of bibliometric data. More specifically, we used Excel to graphically represent the evolution of the number of publications per year, in order to better visualize the temporal dynamics of the research field. This approach enabled us to identify periods of heightened academic interest in the concepts studied, and to illustrate the evolution of scientific production over more than a decade.

Zotero

Finally, Zotero was used to manage and structure bibliographic references, helping to ensure the coherence and quality of the article's final bibliography.

Bibliometric analysis of the co-occurrences associated with the “purchase intention” variable reveals a thematic structuring articulated around two major clusters: on the one hand, behavioral methodologies and approaches, and on the other, marketing levers linked to the brand and the digital environment (Li et al., 2019). The first group, represented by the red clusters, focuses on concepts such as “experience”, “questionnaire”, “platform”, “retailer” and “sem”. This field suggests a strong mobilization of theoretical models (such as TAM or SOR) (Moudden & Balhadj, 2024), often operationalized by empirical surveys based on questionnaires measuring user experience, ease of use or perceived reliability (Lou & Yuan, 2019). A second pole, dominated by the terms “brand”, “social medium”, “influencer”, “advertisement” or “celebrity”, shows a more strategic orientation, focusing on digital communication practices, the effect of sponsored publications, types of content or the perceived credibility of influencers (Petit et al., 2019). These elements confirm the growing role of social networks in shaping purchase intent, in particular through engagement with the brand and visual content. In addition, peripheral concepts such as “e-wom”, “disclosure” or “mouth” signal the impact of social recommendation and digital word-of-mouth, often analyzed according to gender, cultural context (e.g. “India”, ‘Pakistan’), or recent contextual effects (e.g. “Covid”). The map as a whole therefore reflects a convergence between experiential approaches (sensory, emotional), digital practices (influence, visual content, advertising) and brand perception, which are key determinants of purchase intent in online environments (Venkatesh et al., 2016).

This mapping reveals some gaps in the literature. The clear division between behavioral models and marketing strategies points to a limited integration of psychological and practical perspectives. Moreover, emerging factors such as evolving influencer roles and platform-specific dynamics remain underexplored. Cultural and contextual variables are treated as peripheral themes, highlighting the need for more in-depth investigation into how these factors influence purchase intention across diverse digital settings.

Figure N°4: Bibliometric visualization of the relationship between Visual Sensory Marketing, E-reputation, and Purchase Intention.

Source: Created by the author using VOSviewer from a Zotero-based corpus

Following the individual co-occurrence analyses conducted for each of the study's three core variables, visual sensory marketing, online reputation, and purchase intention, this integrated bibliometric map provides a comprehensive visualization of the conceptual intersections that unite these domains within the academic literature. It serves as empirical support for the coherence and relevance of the proposed research model.

At the core of the map, the dominant node “social medium”, demonstrates the pivotal role of social media platforms as both a medium of visual communication and a bridge between brand perception and consumer behavior (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). Related terms such as influencer, disclosure, and interactivity highlight the significance of digital presence and user engagement in shaping brand-consumer dynamics (Ashley & Tuten, 2015).

The green cluster, concentrated around terms such as review, rating, online reputation, seller, and platform, reflects a robust body of work examining how electronic word of mouth (eWOM) and digital evaluations influence brand trust and credibility (Chevalier & Mayzlin, 2006; Luca,

2016). These themes reinforce the idea that online reputation plays a mediating or moderating role in consumer decision-making processes.

The red cluster, focused on keywords like satisfaction, e-commerce, brand trust, purchase intention, and online shopping, groups research contributions that address the determinants of purchase behavior in digital environments. The density of connections in this area underscores the critical influence of brand experience and trust, particularly when shaped by visual and experiential stimuli (Childers et al., 2001; Fiore et al., 2005).

The purple cluster, featuring terms like experiment, valence, visual cue, taste, and shape, signals an increasing reliance on experimental approaches to study the impact of sensory stimuli, especially in terms of visual perception. This aligns with broader developments in sensory marketing and consumer psychology (Elder & Krishna, 2010; Krishna, 2012).

Overall, this integrated co-occurrence map highlights a significant thematic convergence among visual sensory marketing, online reputation, and purchase intention, confirming their conceptual interdependence. However, the analysis also reveals important limitations: the fragmentation between experimental and real-world approaches, the insufficient consideration of cultural and contextual diversity, and the dynamic evolution of digital platforms remain underexplored. Moreover, the complex, bidirectional relationships between sensory stimuli, reputation management, and consumer behavior call for more integrative and process-oriented models. Future research should therefore adopt multidisciplinary frameworks that account for the fluid, context-specific interactions shaping consumer decision-making in increasingly complex online environments.

3.2. Evolution in time

Figure N°5: Annual evolution of scientific publications related to Visual Sensory Marketing, E-reputation, and Purchase Intention (2015–2025)

Source: Author’s own elaboration using Excel, based on selected articles from Web of Science (2025).

The figure illustrates the annual distribution of scientific articles related to the study’s research focus (visual sensory marketing, online reputation, and purchase intention) between 2015 and 2025.

The data reveals a clear upward trend in the number of publications over the past decade, reflecting growing academic interest and relevance in this field. From 76 articles in 2015, the number of publications steadily increased, reaching 254 articles in 2024, which represents a growth of over 230%.

Several notable shifts can be observed:

- **Moderate growth (2015–2019):** The number of publications rose gradually from 76 to 127, indicating the emergence and consolidation of interest in digital and sensory marketing topics during this phase.
- **Acceleration phase (2020–2025):** Starting from 2020, the literature shows a significant increase, likely driven by the global digital transformation, the expansion of e-

commerce, and the increased use of social media platforms following the COVID-19 pandemic (Y. Dwivedi et al., 2020).

- **Peak in 2024:** With 254 articles, the year 2024 marks the highest point of academic output in the dataset, which may indicate a maturity or saturation of the topic in current research.
- **Drop in 2025 (94 articles):** The apparent decline in 2025 is not conclusive, as the year is still ongoing, and the full volume of publications may not yet be indexed or available.

This trend confirms that the intersection of visual communication, digital reputation, and consumer behavior is increasingly considered a strategic research priority in marketing and consumer sciences. It also reinforces the timeliness and relevance of the present study within the current scholarly discourse.

4. General discussion

The combined bibliometric analyses and temporal trends provide a comprehensive overview of how the academic literature has progressively evolved to converge around the intersection of visual sensory marketing, online reputation, and purchase intention. These findings not only confirm the conceptual relevance of this triadic relationship but also highlight its explanatory power in understanding consumer behavior within increasingly digital and visually driven environments.

The thematic density identified across the maps indicates a gradual integration of previously distinct research domains. Visual sensory marketing, traditionally rooted in physical and retail environments, is now expanding into digital contexts, incorporating experiential, emotional, and aesthetic components native to social media platforms. In this shift, visual perception becomes a key strategic asset for shaping brand image, particularly through content disseminated via social media. These platforms act as powerful amplifiers of perception, where visual consistency and design quality significantly influence a brand's online positioning (Hollebeek & Macky, 2019).

The integrated co-occurrence map further supports the interdependence between visual stimuli, digital credibility, and behavioral intention. It confirms that online reputation is not a passive byproduct of consumer experience, but rather a dynamic mediator that links visual brand presence to trust and ultimately, purchase behavior. The influence of visual stimuli, such as packaging design, influencer aesthetics, or visually engaging advertisements, reinforces perceived credibility, drives positive word-of-mouth (e-WOM), and increases the likelihood of

consumer action. These observations align with prior work by (Kim & Johnson, 2016), who identified visual user engagement as a mediating factor in online brand interactions.

Moreover, the chronological evolution of publications between 2015 and 2025 highlights a strong and accelerating scholarly interest in this convergence. The surge in publications observed in 2024 likely reflects both the academic maturity of the field and the broader digital transformation accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic. As noted by (Y. K. Dwivedi et al., 2021), the interplay between experiential marketing, digital branding, and consumer psychology has emerged as a top research priority in marketing scholarship. This reinforces the relevance of developing an integrated conceptual model in which visual sensory marketing serves as an antecedent to online brand reputation, which in turn influences purchase intention. Nonetheless, the critical dimension of this body of research remains limited. There is a notable lack of systematic questioning regarding potential biases, such as the dominance of certain disciplines, regions, or platforms, which may skew the findings and their generalizability. Additionally, the literature often treats the three constructs in relative isolation or through fragmented lenses, without sufficiently addressing the complex, reciprocal interactions and contextual moderators that characterize real-world digital consumer behavior.

In conclusion, this discussion affirms the relevance of the present study's central research question: to understand how visual sensory marketing, when deployed through social media, shapes brand e-reputation and ultimately influences consumers' intention to purchase. The results provide both theoretical justification and empirical grounding for the construction of a conceptual model that integrates visual perception, online credibility, and behavioral intention within a unified analytical framework, while also emphasizing the need for more nuanced and critically reflexive future research.

Conclusion

This study aimed to explore and clarify the academic landscape connecting visual sensory marketing, online reputation, and purchase intention, with a specific focus on their intersection within digital environments, particularly social media platforms. By conducting a structured bibliometric analysis of recent literature from 2015 to 2025, this article identified key thematic clusters, conceptual linkages, and temporal trends that collectively reinforce the theoretical and empirical relevance of the proposed research model.

The findings demonstrate that visual sensory stimuli, such as design, color, packaging, and digital aesthetics, are no longer limited to physical point-of-sale contexts but are actively

shaping brand perception and consumer engagement through visual content on social media. Furthermore, online reputation emerges as a critical mediating construct, influencing how visual brand experiences are received, shared, and transformed into behavioral intentions such as trust, loyalty, and ultimately, purchase.

The integrated co-occurrence map revealed strong conceptual interconnections across the three constructs, validating their inclusion within a unified theoretical framework. The central role of social media in this dynamic, acting both as a communication channel and a credibility filter, further supports the relevance of this research focus in contemporary marketing discourse. In addition, the upward trajectory in publication volume over the past decade confirms the growing academic and managerial interest in this topic.

By synthesizing current knowledge across disciplines such as sensory marketing, digital communication, and consumer psychology, this article provides a solid foundation for the development of an empirical research model. Future studies may build on these insights by testing causal relationships between visual stimuli, reputation perception, and consumer behavior across diverse cultural and technological contexts.

Future research should also explore the moderating effects of emerging digital trends such as augmented reality, live streaming, and personalized content, which may intensify the impact of visual sensory marketing on online reputation and purchase intention. Moreover, longitudinal and cross-cultural studies could provide deeper insights into how these dynamics evolve over time and vary across consumer segments.

From a practical standpoint, marketers are encouraged to invest strategically in the visual consistency and aesthetic quality of their digital content, recognizing its powerful role in shaping brand credibility and consumer trust. Leveraging influencer collaborations and interactive visual formats can further amplify engagement and positive word-of-mouth. Additionally, monitoring and managing online reputation actively through social listening tools becomes essential to respond promptly to consumer feedback and maintain brand equity in fast-changing digital environments.

Ultimately, this research contributes to a deeper understanding of how digital sensory strategies can enhance brand equity and drive consumer decision-making in the evolving landscape of online commerce.

BIBLIOGRAPHIE

- Akerlof, G. A. (1970). The Market for “Lemons”: Quality Uncertainty and the Market Mechanism*. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 84(3), 488–500. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1879431>
- Ashley, C., & Tuten, T. (2015). Creative Strategies in Social Media Marketing: An Exploratory Study of Branded Social Content and Consumer Engagement. *Psychology & Marketing*, 32. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mar.20761>
- Aslam, M. M. (2006). Are You Selling the Right Colour? A Cross-cultural Review of Colour as a Marketing Cue. *Journal of Marketing Communications*, 12(1), 15–30. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13527260500247827>
- Berthon, P. R., Pitt, L. F., Plangger, K., & Shapiro, D. (2012). Marketing meets Web 2.0, social media, and creative consumers: Implications for international marketing strategy. *Business Horizons*, 55(3), 261–271. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2012.01.007>
- Bouaddi, M., Khaldi, S., Lakhliifi, Y., & Chkiriba, D. (2024). L’effet de la publicité en ligne à travers Facebook sur le processus de décision du consommateur. *Revue Française d’Economie et de Gestion*, 5(11). <https://www.revuefreg.fr/index.php/home/article/view/1832>
- Boukabiya, A., & Benaceur, O. (2020). Expérience optimale et intention d’achat: Un examen de la revue de littérature et future perspective. *Revue Française d’Economie et de Gestion*, 1(3). <https://www.revuefreg.fr/index.php/home/article/view/48>
- Chevalier, J. A., & Mayzlin, D. (2006). The Effect of Word of Mouth on Sales: Online Book Reviews. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 43(3), 345–354. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jmkr.43.3.345>
- Childers, T. L., Carr, C. L., Peck, J., & Carson, S. (2001). Hedonic and utilitarian motivations for online retail shopping behavior. *Journal of Retailing*, 77(4), 511–535. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-4359\(01\)00056-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-4359(01)00056-2)
- Cyr, D., Head, M., & Ivanov, A. (2006). Design aesthetics leading to m-loyalty in mobile commerce. *Information & Management*, 43(8), 950–963. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2006.08.009>
- Cyr, D., Head, M., & Larios, H. (2010). Colour appeal in website design within and across cultures: A multi-method evaluation. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, 68(1), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhcs.2009.08.005>
- Dijkmans, C., Kerkhof, P., & Beukeboom, C. J. (2015). A stage to engage: Social media use and corporate reputation. *Tourism Management*, 47, 58–67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2014.09.005>

- Donthu, N., Kumar, S., Mukherjee, D., Pandey, N., & Lim, W. M. (2021). How to conduct a bibliometric analysis: An overview and guidelines. *Journal of Business Research*, 133, 285–296. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.04.070>
- Dwivedi, Y., Ismagilova, E., Hughes, D. L., Carlson, J., Filieri, R., Jacobson, J., Jain, V., Karjaluoto, H., Kefi, H., Krishen, A., Kumar, V., Rahman, M., Raman, R., Rauschnabel, P., Rowley, J., Salo, J., Tran, G., & Wang, Y. (2020). Setting the future of digital and social media marketing research: Perspectives and research propositions. *International Journal of Information Management*, 59, 102168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2020.102168>
- Dwivedi, Y. K., Ismagilova, E., Hughes, D. L., Carlson, J., Filieri, R., Jacobson, J., Jain, V., Karjaluoto, H., Kefi, H., Krishen, A. S., Kumar, V., Rahman, M. M., Raman, R., Rauschnabel, P. A., Rowley, J., Salo, J., Tran, G. A., & Wang, Y. (2021). Setting the future of digital and social media marketing research: Perspectives and research propositions. *International Journal of Information Management*, 59, 102168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2020.102168>
- Ed-Dafali, S., Adardour, Z., Derj, A., Bami, A., & Hussainey, K. (2025). A PRISMA-Based Systematic Review on Economic, Social, and Governance Practices: Insights and Research Agenda. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 34(2), 1896–1916. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.4069>
- Elder, R. S., & Krishna, A. (2010). The Effects of Advertising Copy on Sensory Thoughts and Perceived Taste. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 36(5), 748–756. <https://doi.org/10.1086/605327>
- Fiore, A. M., Jin, H.-J., & Kim, J. (2005). For fun and profit: Hedonic value from image interactivity and responses toward an online store. *Psychology & Marketing*, 22(8), 669–694. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mar.20079>
- Hair, J. F. (with Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., & Anderson, R. E.). (2014). *Multivariate data analysis*. (Seventh edition / Joseph F. Hair, Jr., William C. Black, Barry J. Babin, Rolph E. Anderson., Pearson new international edition.). Pearson.
- Hajli, M. N. (2014). A study of the impact of social media on consumers. *International Journal of Market Research*, 56(3), 387–404. <https://doi.org/10.2501/IJMR-2014-025>
- Hollebeek, L. D., & Macky, K. (2019). Digital Content Marketing's Role in Fostering Consumer Engagement, Trust, and Value: Framework, Fundamental Propositions, and Implications. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 45(1), 27–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intmar.2018.07.003>
- Kaplan, A. M., & Haenlein, M. (2010). Users of the world, unite! The challenges and opportunities of Social Media. *Business Horizons*, 53(1), 59–68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2009.09.003>

- Kim, A. J., & Johnson, K. K. P. (2016). Power of consumers using social media: Examining the influences of brand-related user-generated content on Facebook. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 58, 98–108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2015.12.047>
- Kitchenham, B. (2004). *Procedures for Performing Systematic Reviews*.
- Krishna, A. (2012). An integrative review of sensory marketing: Engaging the senses to affect perception, judgment and behavior. *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, 22(3), 332–351. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcps.2011.08.003>
- Labrecque, L., & Milne, G. (2012). To be or not to be different: Exploration of norms and benefits of color differentiation in the marketplace. *Marketing Letters*, 24. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11002-012-9210-5>
- Li, H., Fang, Y., Lim, K. H., & Wang, Y. (2019). Platform-Based Function Repertoire, Reputation, and Sales Performance of E-Marketplace Sellers. *MIS Quarterly*, 43(1), 207–236. <https://doi.org/10.25300/MISQ/2019/14201>
- Litvin, S. W., Goldsmith, R. E., & Pan, B. (2008). Electronic word-of-mouth in hospitality and tourism management. *Tourism Management*, 29(3), 458–468. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2007.05.011>
- Lou, C., & Yuan, S. (2019). Influencer Marketing: How Message Value and Credibility Affect Consumer Trust of Branded Content on Social Media. *Journal of Interactive Advertising*, 19(1), 58–73. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15252019.2018.1533501>
- Luca, M. (2016). Reviews, Reputation, and Revenue: The Case of Yelp.com. *Harvard Business School Working Papers*, Article 12–016. <https://ideas.repec.org/p/hbs/wpaper/12-016.html>
- Marwan, A., Harkim, H., & Sugiharto, B. (2024). The Impact of Visual Marketing on Purchasing Behavior in E-Commerce: A Case Study in The Fashion Industry. *Golden Ratio of Data in Summary*, 4, 1022–1031. <https://doi.org/10.52970/grdis.v4i2.769>
- Mongeon, P., & Paul-Hus, A. (2016). The journal coverage of Web of Science and Scopus: A comparative analysis. *Scientometrics*, 106(1), 213–228. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-015-1765-5>
- Moudden, M. E., & Balhadj, S. (2024). What is the relationship between risk management and the specific needs of SMEs? *Revue Internationale des Sciences de Gestion*, 7(4), Article 4. <https://www.revue-isg.com/index.php/home/article/view/1821>
- Nambang-Kagnolema, B. (2025). BOUCHE -A-OREILLE ET FIDELITE DE LA CLIENTELE BANCAIRE. *Revue Française d'Economie et de Gestion*, 6(6). <https://www.revuefreg.fr/index.php/home/article/view/2147>
- Ouariti, O. Z., Hamri, M. H., & Qiyad, R. (2020). L' influence du partage des avis d'expériences clients en ligne sur l'intention d'achat, cas des hôtels 5* de la ville d'Agadir. *Revue*

- Internationale des Sciences de Gestion*, 3(2), Article 2. <https://www.revue-isg.com/index.php/home/article/view/264>
- Pavlou, P. A., & Fygenson, M. (2006). Understanding and predicting electronic commerce adoption: An extension of the theory of planned behavior. *MIS Q.*, 30(1), 115–143.
- Pelet, J.-É., & Papadopoulou, P. (2012). The effect of colors of e-commerce websites on consumer mood, memorization and buying intention. *European Journal of Information Systems*, 21(4), 438–467. <https://doi.org/10.1057/ejis.2012.17>
- Petit, O., Velasco, C., & Spence, C. (2019). Digital Sensory Marketing: Integrating New Technologies into Multisensory Online Experience. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 45(1), 42–61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intmar.2018.07.004>
- Schmitt, B. (1999). Experiential Marketing. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 15(1–3), 53–67. <https://doi.org/10.1362/026725799784870496>
- Tranfield, D., Denyer, D., & Smart, P. (2003). Towards a Methodology for Developing Evidence-Informed Management Knowledge by Means of Systematic Review. *British Journal of Management*, 14(3), 207–222. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8551.00375>
- van Eck, N. J., & Waltman, L. (2010). Software survey: VOSviewer, a computer program for bibliometric mapping. *Scientometrics*, 84(2), 523–538. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-009-0146-3>
- Venkatesh, V., Thong, J. Y. L., & Xu, X. (2016). *Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology: A Synthesis and the Road Ahead* (SSRN Scholarly Paper 2800121). Social Science Research Network. <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=2800121>
- Wedel, M., & Pieters, R. (2007). A review of eye-tracking research in marketing. In N. Malhotra (Ed.), *Review of Marketing Research, Volume 4* (pp. 123–146). M.E. Sharpe Inc.